

**To run like a steed and to shine like the sun:
a collexeme analysis of Rigvedic similes**

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1. Introduction

The notion of formula in oral poetry is mostly associated with the work of Milman Parry and his student Albert B. Lord, who showed that the Homeric poems have been composed through the reuse of fixed expressions (formulas) and more flexible schematic patterns (formulaic systems).¹

The strong similarity between formulas and idioms of everyday language was first stressed by Kiparsky.² In recent years, several theoretical frameworks within linguistics, such as corpus linguistics, language acquisition studies, and Construction Grammar,³ have dealt with phenomena related to those typical of formularity in oral poetry, inspiring new approaches to the study of the latter. Among these, the constructionist approach proposed by Bozzone and Pagán Cánovas and Antović likens formulas to idiomatic expressions in everyday language, successfully integrating fixed formulas and formulaic systems characterized by lexical and syntactic flexibility into a unified model.⁴

The new definition of formula appears to particularly suit the formulaic style of the *Rigveda* (RV), a collection of religious hymns composed in Vedic Sanskrit that constitutes the oldest layer of Indic literature. The form of the hymns depends on tradition, i.e., the creations of previous poets. However, in addition to asserting their belonging to a tradition,

¹ Milman Parry, *The Making of Homeric Verse: The Collected Papers of Milman Parry* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971 [1928]); Albert B. Lord, *The Singer of Tales*. Cambridge (MA: Harvard University Press, 1960).

² Paul Kiparsky, "Oral poetry: some linguistic and typological considerations", in *Oral Literature and the Formula*, ed. Benjamin A. Stolz and Richard Stoll Shannon (Ann Arbor: Center for Coordination of Ancient and Modern Studies, 1976), 73–106.

³ Charles J. Fillmore and Paul Kay, *Construction grammar coursebook* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1993); Adele E. Goldberg, *Constructions: a construction grammar approach to argument structure* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995).

⁴ Chiara Bozzone, *Constructions: A New Approach to Formularity, Discourse, and Syntax in Homer* (PhD diss., UCLA, 2014); Cristóbal Pagán Cánovas and Mihailo Antović, "Construction grammar and oral formulaic theory", In *Oral Poetics and Cognitive Science*, ed. Mihailo Antovic and Cristóbal Pagán Cánovas (Berlin/Boston: Walter de Gruyter, 2016), 79–98; Cristóbal Pagán Cánovas and Mihailo Antović, "Formulaic creativity: Oral poetics and cognitive grammar." *Language & Communication* 47 (2016): 66–74.

Vedic poets emphasize the novelty of their compositions, and this tension between tradition and innovation manifests in continuous and deliberate variations in the expression of conventional themes.⁵

This paper tests the constructional approach to the study of Rigvedic formulaic language by presenting a co-varying Collexeme Analysis (CA)⁶ of Rigvedic similes. Co-varying CA measures the degree of associations between different slots of a construction, thus allowing for the individuation of meso-constructions. Rigvedic similes introduced by the comparative markers *ná*, *iva*, and *yáthā* ‘like’ can be regarded as a macro-construction instantiated by more fixed meso-constructions, as several types of similes can be identified based on the semantics of their parameter and standard of comparison.⁷ Thus, taking formulas as variably fixed constructions, CA allows isolating formulaic similes that fall at different points along the continuum between substantive and schematic. The analysis is carried out employing the Rigvedic portion of the Vedic Treebank,⁸ in which all similes have been manually annotated. The use of digital resources allows for the automatic extraction of formulas and their variants, enabling systematic and replicable research.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the new approach to the study of oral-formulaic language based on the framework of Construction Grammar. Section 3 introduces the method of co-varying CA. Section 4 presents the main features of Rigvedic similes in view of oral-formulaic language, while Section 5 illustrates how to apply CA to detect formulaic similes. Section 6 contains the conclusion.

2. Formulas as constructions

Studies on formulaic language originated and primarily developed within Homeric scholarship, thanks to the work of Milman Parry and Albert B. Lord.⁹ Through field research on the then-thriving oral epic tradition in Yugoslavia, these scholars showed that the art of composing epic songs was learned through a process similar to language acquisition,

⁵ Tatyana Y. Elizarenkova, *Language and Style of the Vedic R̥ṣis* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1995), 22–24.

⁶ Anatol Stefanowitsch and Stefan T. Gries, “Covarying collexemes,” *Corpus Linguistics and Linguistic Theory* 1.1 (2005), 1–43.

⁷ Erica Biagetti, *R̥gvedic similes: a corpus-based analysis of their forms and functions* (PhD diss., University of Pavia/University of Bergamo, 2021).

⁸ Oliver Hellwig et al., “The Treebank of Vedic Sanskrit,” in *Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC 2020)*, ed. Nicoletta Calzolari et al. (ACL Anthology, 2020), 5137–5146.

⁹ Parry, *Making of Homeric Verse*; Lord, *Singer of Tales*.

according to a technique they called “oral composition in performance”. The foundation stones of this process were formulas, i.e., “a group of words which is regularly employed under the same metrical conditions to express a given essential idea”,¹⁰ and formulaic systems, i.e., schematic patterns with slots to be filled. Lord also demonstrated that the formulaic systems identified by Parry could be highly productive and served as the starting tool for the mature singer.

Kiparsky was the first to propose a syntactic definition of formula.¹¹ He suggested comparing formulas to idiomatic expressions found in everyday language, distinguishing between flexible idiomatic expressions (1)a and flexible formulas (1)b on the one hand, and fixed idiomatic expressions (2)a and fixed formulas (2)b on the other.

(1) a. *The X-er, the Y-er*

b. [[*álgos*]_{NP} *path-*]_{VP}

‘Feel ... pain’

(2) a. *It takes one to know one.*

b. *ēmos d’ērigéneia phánē rhododáktylos Ēós*

‘As soon as early Dawn appeared, the rosy-fingered’

Recently, Bozzone and Pagán Cánovas and Antović, have further developed the idea of Lord that formulaic language is acquired and functions much like natural language.¹² They proposed studying Homeric and South Slavic compositional techniques through the lens of Construction Grammar. The foundational hypothesis of this theory is that constructions, i.e., recurring pairings of a specific form with a specific function, are the basic units of language.¹³ Any linguistic expression whose features are not fully compositional, and which requires storage in memory falls under the notion of construction: idiomatic expressions are thus constructions, as well as syntactic structures, since they carry meaning, albeit abstract, even before being “filled” with words. Construction Grammar rejects any rigid distinction between lexicon and syntax and represents all grammatical knowledge uniformly along the syntax-

¹⁰ Parry, *Making of Homeric Verse*, 272

¹¹ Kiparsky, “Oral poetry.”

¹² Bozzone, *Constructions*; Pagán Cánovas and Antović, “Construction grammar and oral formulaic theory;” “Formulaic creativity;” Lord, *Singer of Tales*, 22, 36.

¹³ Fillmore and Kay, *Construction grammar*, Goldberg, *Constructions*.

lexicon continuum.¹⁴ It follows that constructions form a gradient along two dimensions: from substantive to schematic (e.g., the idiom *kick the bucket* vs. the transitive construction) and from atomic to complex (e.g., a single word vs. a syntactic construction). Furthermore, constructions constitute a structured inventory of a speaker’s knowledge of the conventions of her language;¹⁵ this inventory is represented in terms of a taxonomic network of constructions, where taxonomic relations describe relationships of schematicity between two constructions.¹⁶ Take for instance (3), where the substantive idiom is an instance of the more schematic idiom *The X-er, the Y-er*.

- (3) a. [The X-er, the Y-er]
 |
 b. [*The bigger they grow, the harder they fall.*]

The new insight of Bozzone and Pagán Cánovas and Antović lies in recognizing that, much like idiomatic expressions, formulas are recurring pairings of a specific form with a specific function and therefore categorize as constructions. The identification of formulas as constructions encompasses various levels of flexibility observed for formulas: they can be schematic (4)a, partially substantive (4)b, and substantive (4)c and, just like other constructions, they form a structured inventory.¹⁷ In addition, the definition of formulas as constructions captures the fact that formulas are stored in the poet’s mind and, beyond the formal level, are defined by their semantic, syntactic, and discursive function.

- (4) a. [—]_{Pron.Obj} [⊖⊖—⊖⊖—]_{Part.Subj} [⊖⊖—]_V [⊖⊖—⊖⊖—X]_{NP.Subj}
 |
 b. [—]_{Pron.Obj} [⊖⊖—⊖⊖—]_{Part.Subj} *proséphē* [⊖⊖—⊖⊖—X]_{NP.Subj}
 |
 c. *tòn d’apameibómenos proséphē pódas ōkùs Akhilleús* (12x)

¹⁴ Goldberg, *Constructions*, 6–7.

¹⁵ Ronald W. Langacker, *Foundations of cognitive grammar* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1987), 63–76.

¹⁶ William Croft and D. Alan Cruse, *Cognitive linguistics* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 262–263.

¹⁷ Bozzone, *Constructions*, 40–41.

Through a series of case studies, Bozzone¹⁸ demonstrates how a constructionist approach to the study of formulaic language can open new avenues of investigation and substantially enhance our linguistic, philological, and literary understanding of Homeric texts. Bozzone also suggests adopting the same approach for the study of other Indo-European and non-Indo-European poetic traditions, especially those less rich in substantive formulas and characterized by networks of lexically flexible constructions.¹⁹ As also suggested by Bozzone, and as we will see in Section 4, this is precisely the case with the RV. Another possible development suggested by Bozzone is the automation of the process of extracting constructional networks.²⁰

3. Co-varying Collexeme Analysis

Collexeme Analysis (CA) can be considered an extension of collocational analysis that takes grammatical structure into account and is specifically aimed at investigating the interaction between lexemes and the constructions they are associated with. In its simplest form, CA starts with a particular construction and investigates which lexemes are strongly attracted or repelled by a particular slot in that construction. By assuming that a word may occur in a construction if it is semantically compatible with the meaning of the construction, CA thus provides an objective way of identifying the meaning of the construction in question.²¹

Besides investigating the preferences or restrictions associated with individual slots in a construction, CA allows investigating potential interactions between (sets of) words occurring in two different slots of the same construction. The version of CA focusing on such question is called co-varying CA and serves as a tool for identifying meso-constructions, i.e. constructions that are more specific either syntactically or semantically/functionally compared to a more abstract macro-construction.²²

¹⁸ Bozzone, *Constuctions*.

¹⁹ Bozzone, *Constructions*, 39, 225.

²⁰ Bozzone, *Constructions*, 142.

²¹ Anatol Stefanowitsch and Stefan T. Gries, "Collostructions: Investigating the interaction of words and constructions." *International journal of corpus linguistics* 8.2 (2003), 213–215.

Stefanowitsch and Gries, *Co-varying Collexeme Analysis*.

²² Thomas Hoffmann, Jakob Horsch, and Thomas Brunner, "The more data, the better: A usage-based account of the English comparative correlative construction," *Cognitive Linguistics* 30.1 (2019): 1–36;

Jakob Horsch, "Slovak comparative correlatives: A usage-based construction grammar account," *Constructions and Frames* 13.2 (2021): 193–229.

The association strength between pairs of lexical items occurring in two different slots of the same construction can be identified by comparing actual frequencies of co-occurrence with expected ones on the basis of a two-by-two distribution table, as in Table 1.

Table 1. Covarying collexeme analysis (Stefanowitsch and Gries 2005: 9)

	M_{slot2} (word M in slot 2)	¬M_{slot2} (all other words in slot 2)
L_{slot1} (word L in slot 1)	<i>Freq</i> (L _{slot1} + M _{slot2})	<i>Freq</i> (L _{slot1} + ¬M _{slot2})
¬L_{slot1} (all other words in slot 1)	<i>Freq</i> (¬L _{slot1} + M _{slot2})	<i>Freq</i> (¬L _{slot1} + ¬M _{slot2})

In the context of CA, the most widely-used association measure is the *p*-value of a Fisher-Yates exact test (*p*_{FYE}). Since the *p*-value is not an intuitive measure, it is common to log transform the *p*-values, so that they range from $-\infty$ (strong repulsion) to $+\infty$ (mutual attraction), with the zero showing the lack of any association. Consequently, log-transformed values exceeding 1.30103 can be regarded as significant.²³

4. Rigvedic similes in view of oral-formulaic language

Studies on Rigvedic formularity agree in attributing a certain degree of flexibility to the compositional technique of the RV: Kiparsky brought this text into the scholarly discussion about oral poetry and formulas pointing out that its compositional technique makes little use of lexically fixed and metrically defined formulas (“ready-made surface formulae”).²⁴ Rather, the RV consists of a texture of so-called “deep-structure” or schematic formulas, which make up the poets’ repertoire, but which take different instantiations in the text thanks to lexical or grammatical substitution, scrambling, semantic reversal, or metrical variation.²⁵

Lindqvist adopts an empirical approach to the study of Rigvedic formulas and meters, which consists in regarding formulaic diction in this text as “a set of formulaic networks or continua, which owe their cohesion to similarities, their extension to differences between

²³ Stefanowitsch and Gries, “Covarying collexemes,” 7.

²⁴ Kiparsky, “Oral poetry,” 99–103.

²⁵ Stephanie W. Jamison and Joel P. Brereton, *The Rigveda: the earliest religious poetry of India* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014), 14; Stephanie W. Jamison, “Rigvedic *viśvátaḥ sīm*, or, Why syntax needs poetics,” in *Mir curad: Studies in honor of Calvert Watkins*, ed. Jay Jasanoff, H. Craig Melchert and Lisi Oliver (Innsbruck: Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Sprachwissenschaft, 1998), 291–299.

words and phrases; or to put it dynamically, their cohesion is due to retention on certain levels, their extension to renewal on other levels”.²⁶ From these observations, it results that constructional networks are pervasive in Rigvedic diction, but that straight formulas can be found only in some cases (see the networks comprising two apparently straight formulas such as *pibā sómam* ‘drink the soma!’ and *áhann áhim* ‘he slew the serpent’).²⁷

Rigvedic similes are a class of comparative constructions introduced by one of the three standard markers (STM) *ná*, *iva*, and *yáthā* (with its unaccented variant *yathā*) ‘like’. They encode similarity between a comparee (CPREE) and a standard (STAND) with respect to some action or property, called parameter (PAR). The standard marker follows either the standard or, when the latter is a complex phrase, its first element. Cf. example (5) and (6):

(5) RV 2.2.8ab

<i>sá</i>	<i>idhāná</i>	<i>uṣáso</i>	<i>rāmiyā</i>	<i>ánu</i>
3SG.NOM	kindle.AOR.3SG.MID	dawn(F).ACC.PL	night(F).ACC.PL	through
<i>súvar</i>	<i>ṇá</i>	<i>dīded</i>	<i>aruṣéṇa</i>	<i>bhānúnā</i>
sun.NOM	like	shine.INJ.PF.3SG	red.INST	radiance.INST
STAND	STM	PAR		

‘On being kindled through (all) the dawns and the nights, like the sun he (= Agni) has shone with red radiance.’

(6) RV 9.103.6

<i>pári</i>	<i>sáptir</i>	<i>ná</i>	<i>vājayúr ...</i>	
around	steed.NOM	like	prize_seeking.NOM	
	STAND-	STM	-STAND	
<i>vyānaśiḥ</i>	<i>pávamāno</i>	<i>ví</i>	<i>dhāvati</i>	
reaching_through.NOM	purify.PTCP.MID.NOM	through	run.3SG	
	CPREE		PAR	

‘Around like a prize-seeking horse [...] reaching through (it), the self-purifying one (= Soma) runs through (the filter).’

Anyone familiar with Rigvedic hymns knows how pervasive similes are in these texts. In some hymns, similes constitute the main structuring device (e.g., RV 2.39 and 10.106 to the Ásvins), in other hymns, they cluster in sections of the text, or are simply scattered throughout it.

²⁶ Urban Lindqvist, *Rigvedic Formulas and Meter* (BoD-Books on Demand, 2015), 32–33.

²⁷ Lindqvist, *Rigvedic Formulas and Meter*, 29–35.

Similes are interesting from the perspective of oral-formulaic language because, although their schema is very productive and often instantiated by hapaxes, they are also highly formulaic as they frequently associate a specific standard with a specific comparee. These associations can be encoded by fixed expressions but are most often expressed by groups of similes characterized by the same semantics but subject to lexical variation. For instance, in similes (7) and (8), we find two different verbs expressing the idea of ‘impelling, causing to go’, *hi-* and *yā-* (mid), and two lexemes encoding the standard ‘horse, racehorse, steed’, namely *ásva-* and *átya-*.

(7) RV 7.7.1ab

<i>prá</i>	<i>vo</i>	<i>devám̐</i>	<i>cit</i>	<i>sahasānám</i>	<i>agním</i>
LP	2PL.DAT	god.ACC	PTC	strong.ACC	Agni.ACC
<i>ásvam̐</i>	<i>ná</i>	<i>vājinaṁ</i>		<i>hiṣe</i>	<i>námobhiḥ</i>
horse.ACC	like	prize_winning.ACC	urge.INJ.AOR.1SG.MID	homage(N).INST.PL	

‘For you I shall urge on Agni like a prizewinning horse, the very god acting with strength, by my homage.’

(8) RV 8.50.5ab

<i>á</i>	<i>naḥ</i>	<i>sóme</i>	<i>svadhvaré</i>
LP	1PL.GEN	soma.LOC	good_at_ceremony.LOC
<i>iyānó</i>		<i>átyo</i>	<i>ná</i> <i>tośate</i>
speed.PTCP.MID.NOM		steed.NOM	like stream.3SG.MID

‘Being sped like a steed, he [=Indra] streams to our soma, good at the ceremony.’

In the next section, we will see that Rigvedic similes can be analyzed by means of co-varying CA to isolate constructions that fall at different points along the continuum between substantive and schematic. CA allows for ‘weighing’ the level of entrenchment of such constructions, as it is based not only on mere frequencies but on the relative frequency of a given pattern, thus allowing to postulate hypotheses about the kind of constructions that made up the poet’s repertoire.

5. Co-varying CA of Rigvedic similes

Rigvedic similes can be regarded as a macro-construction, characterized by the following features: formally (i.e., syntactically), they are always phrasal, they are characterized by case agreement between comparee and standard, and the standard marker follows (the first element of) the standard; functionally (i.e., semantically), they specialize for figurative comparison. They have either generic standards that belong to the natural world, or specific

standards that represent a prototypical instantiation of the quality expressed by the parameter. Thus, Rigvedic similes may be schematically represented as in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of Rigvedic similes.

The co-varying CA presented below is based on all similes featuring a verbal parameter in the RV (which constitute the majority, totaling 1,829 similes) and focuses on the two slots that most characterize similes, namely the PAR and the STAND slot.²⁸ All similes have been annotated within the Vedic Treebank, a morpho-syntactically annotated corpus of Vedic texts. In addition, all similes have been annotated for two variables: the Lexical filler of PAR and STAND and their Semantic class. The integration of the latter variable is due to the already mentioned preference of Rigvedic diction for lexical variation and is aimed at capturing groups of similes that share the same semantics while displaying lexical variation. For instance, the two similes in (7) and (8) above employ different Lexical fillers but they both contain a Cause_motion verb and their standards both refer to a Horse.

The analysis was performed drawing on the {collustruction} package for R, v.0.2.0, by Susanne Flach.²⁹ Out of 1,829 analyzed similes, 1,573 different Lexical filler pairs were found, 1,406 of which were hapaxes; similarly, the Semantic class pairs were 1,121, among which 824 were hapaxes, attesting to the productivity of the two constructional slots.

At the same time, the co-varying CA analysis retrieved significantly associated Lexical filler and Semantic class pairs. Due to the large number of hapaxes, the analysis also identified as significant many pairs that only appeared once in the data, which from a linguistic perspective is misleading. Therefore, Table 2 and Table 3 only list the most significantly associated Lexical filler and Semantic class pairs among those with at least five observations.

²⁸ For this study I have only considered verbal parameters because annotation requires a substantial amount of manual work. The same analysis can be extended to non-verbal parameters as well – perhaps by adding the part of speech of the parameter as a further variable – and to other slots of the construction.

²⁹ Susanne Flach, *Collostructions: An R implementation for the family of collostructional methods*. Package version v.0.2.0, 2021, <https://sfla.ch/collostructions/>.

In both tables, columns PAR and STAND contain items occurring in the PAR and STAND slots respectively, while columns fPAR and fSTAND contain their frequency within similes. OBS indicates the number of observations of the pair, p_{FYE} its collustration strength (log-transformed p -values), with SIGNIF indicating the significance of the association.

The potential of co-varying CA for the analysis of Rigvedic similes and of formulas in general lies in its ability to determine, through collustration strength, the statistical significance of the association between elements occurring in two slots of a macro-construction. Such an association constitutes a clue for the existence of a more substantive meso-construction involving the elements in question. In other words, while the absolute number of observations of a pair might lead to impressionistic judgments about the existence of variably fixed meso-constructions, co-varying CA allows us to assess the statistical relevance of an association and, consequently, the degree of formularity of the expression in which it occurs.

For reason of space, in what follow I will comment on one pair in each table only.

Table 2. Most attracted covarying collexemes (Lexical fillers) in Rigvedic similes.

PAR	STAND	fPAR	fSTAND	OBS	p_{FYE}	SIGNIF
<i>pyā</i> - 'swell'	<i>nadī</i> - 'river'	22	8	8	15.98069	*****
<i>vṛt</i> - 'roll'	<i>cakra</i> - 'wheel'	25	14	7	9.93707	*****
<i>sad</i> - 'sit'	<i>śyēna</i> - 'falcon'	30	22	8	9.27912	*****
<i>pū</i> - 'purify'	<i>ghṛtā</i> - 'butter'	11	13	5	8.46484	*****
<i>pat</i> - 'fly'	<i>vī</i> - 'bird'	26	20	6	6.81939	*****
<i>tan</i> - 'extend'	<i>sūrya</i> - 'sun'	18	33	6	6.466	*****
<i>pr</i> - 'bring over, rescue'	<i>rātha</i> - 'chariot'	27	38	6	4.93854	****
<i>srj</i> - 'let go, cast'	<i>ātya</i> - 'steed'	36	35	6	4.39183	****

Table 3. Most attracted Semantic class pairs in Rigvedic similes.

PAR	STAND	fPAR	fSTAND	OBS	p_{FYE}	SIGNIF
Create	Artisan	45	33	14	14.70323	*****
Moving_In_Place	Wheel	51	24	12	12.91949	*****
Fluidic_Motion	Water	73	112	22	10.26971	*****
Light_Movement	Sun	62	59	15	9.69293	*****
Clothing	Garment	11	9	5	9.46808	*****
Milking	Cow	10	89	8	9.01651	*****

Light_Movement	Fire	62	19	8	7.20393	*****
Emotions_Of_Mental_Activity	Young_Man	27	28	7	7.19298	*****
Expansion	Water	89	112	20	6.90473	*****
Removing	Butter	18	15	5	6.84381	*****
Assistance	Father	16	19	5	6.55325	*****
Posture	Falcon	66	22	8	6.39447	*****
Grooming	Horse	84	157	22	6.11775	*****
Light_Movement	Gold	62	8	5	5.70355	*****
Traversing	Boat	52	10	5	5.45927	*****

As Table 2 shows, the most attracted Lexical filler pair is the one featuring the verb *pyā-* ‘swell’ in the PAR slot and the noun *nadī-* ‘river’ in the STAND slot. The eight occurrences of this combination are all instantiated by the refrain in (9), found at the closing of hymns of the Vāmadeva Indra cycle, i.e., a series of hymns dedicated to Indra and attributed to the poet Vāmadeva. Since this combination is always found within the same fixed formula, we can talk of a fully substantive construction; furthermore, we can see it as a signature of this particular poet, rather than as a feature of Rigvedic diction as a whole.

(9) RV 4.16.21, 4.17.21, 4.19.11, 4.20.11, 4.21.11, 4.22.11, 4.23.11, 19-24.11

nú *ṣṭutá* *indra* *nú* *grṇānáḥ*
now praise.PPP.NOM Indra.VOC now sing.PTCP.MID.NOM
īṣaṁ *jaritré* *nadyò* *ná* *pīpeḥ*
refreshment(F).ACC singer.DAT river(F).NOM.PL like swell.INJ.PF.2SG

‘Now praised, o Indra, now being sung, make refreshment swell for the singer like rivers.’

Let’s now turn to attracted Semantic class pairs in Table 3. At the bottom of the table, we find the combination of a parameter expressing Expansion with a standard referring to Water. Some instances of this pairing are found within the refrain at the closing of hymns belonging to the Vāmadeva Indra cycle, which we have just seen in example (9) and which features the lexical fillers *pyā-* ‘swell’ and *nadī-* ‘river’. Other lexical fillers occurring in this combination are presented in Table 4. Examples (10) to (13) provides further instances.

Table 4. Lexical fillers for Expansion and Water.

PAR: Expansion	STAND: Water	OBS
<i>prath-</i> ‘extend’	<i>síndhu-</i> ‘river’	1

<i>pinv-</i> ‘swell’	<i>áp-</i> ‘water’	2
<i>pinv-</i> ‘swell’	<i>nabhanú-</i> ‘spring’	1
<i>pyā-</i> ‘swell’	<i>nadī-</i> ‘river’	8
<i>pyā-</i> ‘swell’	<i>áp-</i> ‘water’	1
<i>pyā-</i> ‘swell’	<i>avatá-</i> ‘fountain’	1
<i>pyā-</i> ‘swell’	<i>rása-</i> ‘stream’	1
<i>pyā-</i> ‘swell’	<i>útsa-</i> ‘spring’	1
<i>uruṣy-</i> ‘make space’	<i>áp-</i> ‘water’	1
<i>vṛdh-</i> ‘grow, make grow’	<i>vār-</i> ‘water’	1
<i>vṛdh-</i> ‘grow, make grow’	<i>síndhu-</i> ‘river’	2

(10) RV 10.62.9cd (*prath-*)

sāvarṇiyásya *dákṣiṇā*
Sāvarṇya.GEN priesty_gift(F).NOM
ví ***síndhur*** ***iva*** ***paprathe***
out river.NOM like spread.PF.3SG.MID
‘The priestly gift of Sāvarṇya spreads out like a river.’

(11) RV 8.49.2cd (*pinv-*)

girér ***iva*** ***prá*** ***rásā*** ***asya*** ***pinvire***
mountain.ABL like forth juice.NOM.PL 3SG.GEN swell.3SG.MID
dátrāṇi ***purubhójasaḥ***
gift(N).NOM.PL much_nurishing.GEN
‘Like the juices [=streams] of a much-nourishing mountain his (Indra’s) gifts swell forth.’

(12) RV 1.63.8ab (*pyā-*)

tuvám *tyám* *na* *indara deva* *citrám*
2SG.NOM DEM.ACC.F 1SG.DAT Indra.VOC god.VOC bright.ACC.F
íṣam ***ápo*** ***ná*** ***pīpayah*** ***párijman***
refreshment(F).ACC water(F).ACC.PL like swell.CAUS.SUBJ.PF.3SG circling.LOC
‘You, god Indra, will make this bright refreshment swell for us as waters do in their circling.’

(13) RV 8.50.6cd (*pyā-*)

udrī ***iva*** ***vajrinn*** ***avató*** ***vasutvaná***
watery.NOM like mace-bearer.VOC wellspring.NOM good(N).INST
sádā ***pīpetha*** ***dāśúṣe***
always swell.PF.2SG pious.DAT
‘Like a wellspring full of water, mace-bearer, you always swell with goods for the pious man.’

From a closer look at the examples, it emerges that similes featuring the parameters *pyā*- ‘swell’, *pīnv-* ‘id.’, and *prath-* ‘extend’ compare the abundance of a god’s reward for his devotees (*dātra-* ‘gift’, *dākiṣiṇā-* ‘priestly gift’, *īṣa-* ‘refreshment’, *vasutvanā-* ‘wealth, riches’) to the swelling of waters. Therefore, we can isolate a meso-construction in which not only the standard and the parameter are semantically specified but the comparee as well, which we could subsume under the headword Reward. The resulting sub-construction is schematized in (14); a sub-construction inheriting from (14) selects the verb *pyā-* ‘swell’ as parameter (15).

(14) [Water_{STAND} *ná/iva*_{STM} Expansion_{PAR} Reward_{CPREE}]

|

(15) [Water_{STAND} *ná/iva*_{STM} *pyā-*_{PAR} Reward_{CPREE}]

Among those presented in Table 3, the combination of *vṛdh-* ‘grow, make grow’ and *síndhu-* ‘river’ or *vār-* ‘water’ makes up similes that deviate somewhat in form and meaning from the construction in (14). Indeed, such similes compare prayers that make Indra grow to rivers that swell the sea; the sea (*samudrá-*) can be explicitly mentioned, as in (16), or only implicitly, as in RV 2.11.2 and 8.98.8.

(16) RV 8.6.35ab (*vṛdh-*)

<i>índram</i>	<i>ukthāni</i>	<i>vāvṛdhuḥ</i>
Indra.ACC	recitation(N).NOM.PL	increase.PF.3PL
<i>samudrám</i>	<i>iva</i>	<i>síndhavaḥ</i>
sea.ACC	like	river.NOM.PL

‘Their recitations have increased Indra, like the rivers the sea.’

Such similes can be schematically represented as in (17). Note that, differently from the one in (14), the meso-construction in (17) specifies the case of both arguments depending on *vṛdh-*. In (14), the Reward in the comparee can take both the nominative and the accusative case and the same holds for the standard Water; in (17), on the other hand, Prayers are always in the nominative case and Indra always in the accusative, and the same configuration is found for Water and Ocean in the standard.

(17) [[Water-NOM (Ocean-ACC)]_{STAND} *ná/iva*_{STM} *vṛdh-*_{PAR} [Prayers-NOM Indra-ACC]_{CPREE}]

Another simile deviating from the construction in (14) features the denominal verb *uruṣay-* ‘make space, look for space’ as parameter and *áp-* ‘water’ as standard, comparing Agni growing among the fire-churning sticks (metaphorically referred to as *pitarór upásthe* ‘the lap of his parents’) to waters making space in their downward course (cf. RV 3.5.8cd).

As the examples above show, data in Table 2 and Table 3 allow postulating a structured inventory of constructions, in which more substantive constructions inherit features from the more schematic ones. The inventory can be represented as a taxonomic network, as in Figure 2.

6. Conclusion

Adopting the new constructionist approach to the study of formulas, this paper proposed a novel method for extracting variably substantive formulas from a text. The method, based on co-varying CA, has been tested on an annotated version of the RV, specifically focusing on a type of constructions, namely Rigvedic similes.

Starting from a schematic macro-construction, the analysis has enabled the identification of statistically significant associations between two slots within it, namely the PAR and the STAND slot, thereby allowing for the individuation of more substantive meso-constructions; additionally, fully substantive constructions were identified. The results of co-varying CA point to the existence of a structured inventory of constructions in which the more substantive constructions inherit features from the more schematic ones, and which can be represented as a structured network. When it comes to similes, we can postulate that such an inventory formed the poet’s repertoire and allowed him to produce novel comparisons while at the same time remaining within the limits imposed by tradition.

In conclusion, the method employed in this paper seems promising both from an empirical perspective, as it allows for the automatic extraction of variably substantive formulas, and from a cognitive perspective, as it enables the formulation of hypotheses about the kind of constructions that made up the poet’s repertoire and, therefore, about the mechanisms that regulated oral poetic composition in ancient India.

Figure 2. Taxonomic network of constructions.

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